

Evaluating the Effectiveness of Boardrooms in Family-Owned Businesses: A Study on Strategic Benefits and Decision-Making Impact

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ABSTRACT: Boardrooms are the major concern in making and implementing the strategies and organizational main goals. Corporate boards are accountable for major corporate decisions and the effectiveness of such decisions is dependent on the characteristics of the board. The main purpose of this research is to find out the most effective and the least effective benefits of having boardrooms specifically in the family owned business. This will help the family owned business to understand the significance and the benefits of boardrooms, so that they can better utilize the boardrooms to enhance the effectiveness of their businesses. For achieving the task researcher prepare the bi-polar questionnaire on the basis of the model of benefits of boardrooms and for the responses the experts were used to fill the bi-polar questionnaire, on the basis of their experience in the boardrooms. For the analysis of this entire process Excel and the Expert Choice software used to complete the analysis and the construction of the results. This research also tells that evaluating the CEO and fundraising are showing positive association towards boardrooms effectiveness. Moreover, fundraising also, a consistent factor that highly attracted towards boardrooms with sub dimensions of funding proposal it will also provide better insight of the financial positions and activities these fundraising activities takes place in different aspects to plan for the potential loses that could take place. Certainly, the most and least significant factors could be finding and these factors will be considered with boardrooms to create effective process.

Keywords: Boardrooms, Effectiveness, Family businesses, Analytical hierarchical Process, Bi-polar

1. Introduction

Boardrooms are the ultimate power and focus of strategizing and executing the major objectives and aims of the organization. It is clear that its arrangement must be responsive to the basic functions that are allocated to it: supervisory and controlling roles aimed at preventing self-serving actions from managerial agents and offering recommendations to key managers for the efficient handling of the enterprise. These aspects have been considered by the scholars who have examined whether the factors that drive the composition of boards are linked to the basic roles assigned and whether the mentioned composition influences the management of the business (Achanga, Cordoba, &

Rios, 2017; Borlea et al., 2017; Cavaco et al., 2017; Farag & Mallin, 2017; Idrees et. al., 2022)

Corporate boards are responsible for most of the organizational decisions that affect the operation of a business (Chen et al. 2017), and the ability of such decisions to deliver on the intended impact is informed by the nature, composition, and structure of the board. As pointed out in the previous section, prior literature predominantly concentrates the board characteristics' link with corporate productivity (Hu et al., 2010; Van Essen et al., 2012). Several research articles have focused on the relationship in the structure of the board of directors on organizational innovation. This simply means that organizations trying as hard as ever to remain competitive in the market by innovating and creating a competitive advantage that will make them be unique in the market. This research topic is one of the most explored in business today because the topic relates to innovation. (Ladki & Ahmad, 2018). To adopt the above investigation, it was evidenced that only a few studies were conducted in the context of Pakistan to discern the institutional factors influencing the CG practices.

Among all the studies conducted the most relevant research was done by Arslan et al. (2019). Making this study quite relevant, however it was also different in some ways on the following basis. Consequently, this study has its own implications and contribution to the academia as well as to the ones who are in policy-making division. The research paper of Arslan et al., (2019) was more focused on the quantitative method of data collection through survey interviews, thus lacks the qualitative analysis of the results. However, scholars called for research about CG from a qualitative standpoint Aguilera and Jackson (2010). The understanding that there are gaps in the work and the qualitative findings motivates us to extend the work and provide more details on the research. Hence, this study is solely based on the qualitative research technique (semi-structured interviews) and data analysed in the present study are endorsed with the help of previous theories and researches. The behaviours exhibited and/or features possessed by Family businesses make these companies to be different from the non-Family business.

These include the degree of succession necessity, financial results, business and the age of the business, corporate governance, management and ownership. There is Koutra et. al. (2018) study on the perceptions of Greek-Cypriots towards sexual violence and the role of culture in this perspective: In detail, prior literature has shown that family governance of FFSs has not received substantial attention as compared to governance in other organizations and that little analytical work has been done to consider the contextually of family firm governance systems in different contexts (Le Breton-Miller and Miller, 2009; Cesar and Magdy, 2016). Much of what has been written about family-business boards looks at the characteristics of the boards and how they correlate with the performance of the firm (Zattoni et al., 2015), whereas the concept of what goes on behind closed doors has not received much attention (Ikähei- mänen, 2014).

Pakistan's during the recent past has showed a massive economic growth and as an outcome of it, a large number of organizations are unlisted, most of them belong to the family operated firms. According to the Securities & Exchange Commission of Pakistan it has been revealed that the total of non-listed companies have crossed the figure of fifty-five

thousand as against to the listed companies these are five thousand numbers (Gulzar & Wang 2010).

Out of all the factors of importance of having a boardroom, which of them is most important and on the other hand, which of the factors is least important. This research will help the family owned business to grasp the importance of boardroom and the significant and insignificant benefits of boardrooms. This has applied the technique known as Analytical hierarchical approach (AHP) which is normally applied to determine both the most and the least important factors as per the response given by the expert Board members in this study. First of all, the factors of the successful healthcare construction and benefits to sort out based on the research papers and examined the relevance of the previously identified factors in the context of Pakistan. In detail, this research seeks to identify the benefit on boardrooms that elicits the most positive response from the two types of business and the benefit that receives the least amount of positive response from the two types of business, with an emphasis on family owned business. This way the family owned businesses will be empowered with knowledge on the importance of boardrooms and take the advantage to improve their business hence maximizing on the efficiency of boardrooms. One of the reasons for such a conclusion is the fact that this research is different from the ones available for analysis, and the nature and construction of this work are also unique since the analytical hierarchical approach is not applied to evaluate the boardrooms. Moreover, distinguishing between the advantages of boardrooms for the family owned business is another specific aspect of the research that will unlock the potential for this field of study in to the multiple opportunities.

2. Literature Review

Similarly, there has been growing interest demonstrated by academicians in how CEO-boards affiliation affects the work of a board. According to the tenets of empirical research, the authors hypothesize that the absence of social independence from the management negotiates how the board of directors will affect the strategy formulation process. For instance, it is recommended that CEOs maintain their boards as asleep and less participating in strategic decisions through co-optation. They are supposed to be in charge of the organizations that are non-profit and ensure that the organizations follow all the laws that govern ethical and legal aspects. Thus it could be stated that legal, domination, and ethical responsibilities are based on the firm's subject area financial perspectives. In its turn, the active participation of the members of board with the basic knowledge of budgets, financial statements, and, main non-profit tax law is of great importance.

Other essential practices include grants application, fundraising, funding proposal timing, the capitalization reserve, investment policy monitoring and all-round financial NSOPs. From the agency model for the board as a controlled mechanism, there is evidence that boards are less reactive from the broad and more mixed perspective with non-executive directors involved in providing advice and improving strategies. According to Lorsch and Maclver (1989), the surveyed directors in their study reported that supervising

management and being an advisory body are considered by many directors to be 'board's fundamental routine responsibilities'. Demb, Stephen, and Neubauer, Ottensmeyer. 1992. *Corporate Downsizing: A Research Agenda on an Emerging Phenomenon*. Two broad relationship types were defined as competitive and complementary with major distinctions in terms of board impact. This paper has found that there are two significant understandings regarding the separation of the roles of chairman and chief executives acceptable in that it has helped to address issues of excessive executive powers and improved non-executive's board independence (Cadbury, 1992).

Board's work and functioning is stated to be empirically distinctive and the extent of boards' active engagement and impact on the host firm will depend not only on external circumstances and board structures but on the board processes, motivation and skills of a directorial board as a working team (Pettigrew and McNulty, 1998). Forbes and Milliken have tried to build a foundation for their assertion that boards work under social-psychological processes involving group participation in the exchange of information and critical discussion. In this they seek to explain that an ideal board should serve a distinguishing service and control function well (task effectiveness), although individual board members may still want to continue working together (cohesiveness). Still, both these resulted criteria are pertaining different objectives and goals, but both enhance the firm performance. The proposed linearity of the interaction of board task performance and cohesiveness is posited as curvilinear. As Davis et al. (1997) aptly pointed out, task performance by board's needs 'intensive communication and discussion, and board members must have a certain minimum degree of Interpersonal attraction or liking in order to indulge in these activities ... [they] must rely on the competence and capabilities of other board directors' (Forbes and Milliken, 1999,

Using the assumption within agency theory, having non-executives with special independence as the board can enhance the efficiency of these mechanisms through direct monitoring and the effective use off remunerations (rewards) and penalties (executive dismissal). These mechanisms deliberately address an aspect that was considered by the executive in his/her self-serving calculus, the positive or negative. It can barely be viewed as limiting, but rather as actively gesturing toward and offering an eager release for the kind of naked self-interest that they eagerly anticipate will be on tap when the respective alignments come into view. However, always having non-executives present at board-related meetings has other, fairly unfamiliar and plural opportunities to hold to account.

In fact, the evidence showing the relationship between boards Which prolongs the monitoring practices as per the high standards set by it and enhances the performance of the organization is a rather mixed one (Hillman and Dalziel, 2003). Therefore, these views, support the assertion by Fama and Jensen (1983) that the focal donors play a monitoring role which in an organization, is complemented by their "investment". This makes it easy for them to strongly support the assurance of efficiency within the organization due to their financial investment on the very organization.

Hence the aim is to systematically review, evaluate and build upon current understanding and conscientiousness concerning: (i) the theoretical literature on understanding of why and how board diversification affects a broad array of firm's financial

and non-financial performance characteristics such as risks, efficiencies, CSR, and remunerations. (ii) the empirical evidence on the same subject. Besides, the research model includes the following financial institutions performance measures: The chief executive officer (CEO) pay and a numerous set of performance measures, such as merger and acquisition (M&A) of businesses, earnings management, intellectual capital, innovation and ethical reputation.

Its introduction in the form of a performance evaluation of the CEO testifies to its effectiveness in regulating the manner in which it is done on maintaining the balance on how it operates in a part of the CEO's compensation but depends on achieving the goals related to boards. Specifically, the technique of appraisal has been made clear in the insert "Evaluating the CEO". Appraising Boardroom Performance Jay A. Conger, David Finegold, and Edward E. Lawler III. Herman and Renz (1997) actualized that the levels of boards that possessed an organized method of assessing the CEO performances occurred to be more evolved in efficient companies. Generally, though, research with agency theory has yielded some mixed views on the relationship between board performance and measures of organizational performance, (Miller, 2002). Green and Griesinger (1996) noted that Board of governance that got involved in resource-procurement and on contribution of personal funds which were activities related to resource provision improved and enhanced the measures of organizational performance that included improvisation and augmentation. Augmenting the board member occupational diversification was positively related to organizational performance including social responsibility and capability to raise funds as observed by Siciliano in 1996. Studies on academic boards have also indicated a growing attention on how the relationships between the CEO and the board affect the performance of the boards more. Researchers have postulated that when boards are not socially independent from management, this might possibly sub-optimize board contribution to strategizing.

It also got proposed in example that the CEOs keep their boards most passive and non-strategic co-optation or by populating boards with their followers (for example, Herman, 1981; Mace, 1986; Wade, O'Reilly and Chandratat, 1990). The significantly positive impact of financial incentives for remuneration and improvements in agency theory suggests that the introduction of financial incentives, or a small degree of incentive alignment can achieve considerable agency cost reductions (Rediker & Seth, 1995; Zajac and West-phal, 1994). Still, many research works have indicated that the percentage of a board nominated by a CEO has a potential to bolster the board for the leadership of a CEO. Some research has linked Jeffrey D. polymerization of CEOs to the proportion of CEOs, the size of CEO reward packages, and the explanations for CEO incentive remuneration as well as to the endorsement of anti-takeover measures (Lambert, Larcker, & Weigelt, 1993; Main, O'Reilly, & Wade, 1995; Zajac & Westphal, As pointed out by Kang et al., (2007, p. 195) , board diversity maybe defined in a manner that refers to the diversity of the board of directors and this kind of diversity has two elements that are directly observable. The more overt one is primary sociodemographic status of nationality, age, gender and ethnic origins The other more hidden or submerged or removed one is educational, functional and occupational status.

3. Methodologies

This research simply seeks to identify and explore key factors relating to board rooms. To accomplish the task researcher has developed the bi-polar questionnaire with the help of a model that reveals the benefits of boardrooms and to elicit the responses the experts were asked to complete the bi-polar questionnaire in light of their experience with boardrooms. Bi polar is known to determine percentages concerning the ratings given on the basic dimensions and sub dimensions in an ascending order or a descending order. It works by the scale of 1 to 9 where 5 is the midpoint and 9 fancying is highly extremely agreeing or focus when selecting between factors. The responses of the experts were entered into an expert choice, and it gives each experts' individual pair wise matrix as well as the cumulative matrix. haring of judgment matrix for pair wise comparison gives local weights and the Global weights provides the importance of the sub dimension in terms of the dimension.

The corresponding measurements and sub measurements are prioritized first, and the priority has been set up to describe the measurements and sub measurements. Secondly, the responses of Bi-polar questionnaire will be recorded in the expert choice by developing the respondent sheet. Finally, then the individual responses compared for the pair wise and then the combine individual option channelized by which the software makes the PCJM and the internal consistencies appear at last. When it comes to the analysis of this whole process, one would have to make use of the Excel and the Expert Choice software used to carry out the analysis as well as construction of this result. Another point made by (Goodhew, 2009) is that in a similar way, any potential when examined via a single domain cannot be identified through different strategies and measurement could be done

It is run through certain process, these are identification, selection and prioritization and there are three levels.

Stage 1: Identification

In the first step researcher has distinguished also the potential dimensions and sub dimensions of the board rooms discussed in many studies (Becker, 1962; Abdullah, Jaafar, & Taib, 2013).

Stage 2: Selection

Technique # 2: Selection dimensions and sub dimensions from literature After you find out about second step, let me include all dimensions & sub-dimensions that will be relevant on the effectiveness of board's room in Pakistan. For this Likert scale the number 3 is chosen and the scale used is; 1= is most important, 2= is slightly important, 3=least important. To obtain the Questionnaire distributed to the family-owned business person, it is shown in the table 1.

Stage 3: Prioritization

At this stage the dimensions and sub dimensions that itself created on bi-polar scales The Saaty's scale set which is developed by Saaty (1980) Here in the survey, we

also identified the most & least important factors from the respondents' point of view. Other than such respondents, AHP procedure identified here most and least important are the scales of bipolar questionnaire as suggested by Saaty (2005) the scale should be used for the scale of 1 to 9 as shown below Saaty's Scale of Relative Importance.

Intensity of importance	Definition
1	Equal importance
3	Somewhat more important
5	Much more important
7	Very much more important
9	Absolutely more important
2, 4, 6, 8	Intermediate values

Figure 1: The Analytic Hierarchy Process

4. Results and Analysis

Source: Puyvelde1 et. al. (2018)

Figure 2: Hierarchies of Dimensions & Sub Dimensions

For the above hierarchy of dimension and sub dimensions concerning the board rooms chosen out of the responses, we can see from the above hierarchy. The above Hierarchy demonstrate about the 06 dimension evaluated i:M MPO, financial oversight (FO, Evaluation and assessment of the CEO (EC), Consultation and assistance to the CEO (PGS), Fund raising (FR), Community Relations and Outreach (CRO. Furthermore, every factor has 3 sub dimensions, and in total 18 sub dimension are assessed during test and survey.

Combine instance—Synthesis with respect to Board Rooms

Main Dimensions & Sub Dimensions

Figure 3: Model AHP Synthesis Summaries

Percentage required for board room is depicted through the weights used in the above figure and all values are thus computed from the responses collected from the respondents by finding out the highest and lowest percentage about the total. As we have seen, the task of Evaluating to the CEO has the highest score of 0. 20 on its sub dimension of intellectual capital, earning management as well as Merger &Acquistions indicating the values of 0. 247, 0. 224 and 0. Chorley’s rank have highest and revealed association with boardrooms The 529 are rank has highest and display association with boardrooms. On the other hand, community reach out and relation has least significant association with value of 0. and of the 4 the order sub-dimensions’ mutual relations, Board compositions and competitive advantage got values 0. 387,0. 3730. 239 respectively giving lest importance among overall aspects.

Table-1 Pairwise Comparison Judgement Matrix-----Main Dimension

Board Rooms	MOP	FO	EC	PGS	FR	CRO	Priority
Monitoring Organizational Performance	0.15	0.17	0.10	0.30	0.15	0.14	0.17
Financial Oversight	0.14	0.16	0.11	0.10	0.18	0.20	0.15
Evaluating the CEO	0.29	0.26	0.19	0.14	0.15	0.15	0.20
Provide Guidance & Support to CEO	0.08	0.22	0.18	0.14	0.20	0.13	0.16
Fundraising	0.16	0.16	0.22	0.12	0.18	0.22	0.18
Community relation & outreach	0.15	0.11	0.17	0.17	0.11	0.14	0.14
Consistency Ratio							0.07

Table 1 represents about the calculation related to the main dimensions of Boardrooms. Above Outcome appraisal values developed using the method of Geo-mean as suggested by (Barzilai, Goolany, & Goolany, 1987). When comparing out the comparative importance between variables, the technique adopted is Pairwise comparison judgment matrix PCJMA geo-mean method, which is one of the most popular ways. Additional geo-mean recorded and responses shown among below table 3 which contains the individual responses of the Boardrooms, assessed from the filled questionnaire. Likewise, the diagonal values are of 01 that remains same throughout the construct as the manifest variables of the construct are same. As presented from the above table that depicts the value of Monitoring organizational performance with financial oversight 1/7 row wise and in the 0 column. 14, thus in the end respondent has preferred monitoring of organizational performance over financial performance since it is being compared. Similar to the step for 40 responses, though this is supported by (Saaty, 1980); (Lootsma, 1980) while geo-mean is one of the ways of determining normalized weights.

However, to that, geo-mean is imposed on each dimension and response from individuals and then arithmetic mean taking with priority for calculating local weights that signifies the importance regarding with Boardrooms. Of all the factors the most preferred is the option of appraising the CEO with 0. 20. In the second & third position is fundraising & monitoring organizational performance with 0. 18, 0. 17 respectively. The same process is followed in case of the sub dimensions to determine the most dominating factor out of these sub dimensions.

Table-02 Individual Response of One Responded

Board Rooms	MOP	FO	EC	PGS	FR	CRO
Monitoring Organizational Performance	1	1/2	1/4	3	1/7	8
Financial Oversight	2	1	2	1/2	1/7	9
Evaluating the CEO	4	1/2	1	1/7	1/3	6
Provide Guidance & Support to CEO	1/3	5	7	1	4	1/2
Fundraising	7	7	3	4	1	2
Community relation & outreach	1/8	1/9	1/6	3	1/2	1

Table-03 Pairwise Comparison Judgement Matrix-----Sub Dimensions

Monitoring Organizational Performance	MBO	BSC	TQM	Priority
MBO	0.33	0.46	0.27	0.36
Balanced score card	0.21	0.31	0.41	0.32
Total Quality Management	0.23	0.23	0.33	0.33
Consistency Ratio				0.07
Financial Oversight	ROA	FL	LQ	Priority
Return on Assets	0.22	0.28	0.17	0.21
Financial Leverage	0.22	0.32	0.39	0.32
Liquidity	0.57	0.39	0.46	0.48
Consistency Ratio				0.06
Evaluating the CEO	MA	EM	IM	Priority
Merger & Acquisitions	0.51	0.66	0.41	0.52
Earning Management	0.16	0.18	0.31	0.21
Intellectual Management	0.32	0.17	0.27	0.26
Consistency Ratio				0.09
Providing Guidance & Support to CEO	IA	LD	SF	Priority
Incentive alignment	0.47	0.61	0.38	0.48
Leadership	0.16	0.22	0.32	0.23
Social Factor	0.36	0.19	0.29	0.28
Consistency Ratio				0.08
Fundraising	FP	CRF	IP	Priority
Funding Proposal	0.31	0.41	0.22	0.32
Capital Reserve Funds	0.23	0.34	0.46	0.33
Investment Policy	0.47	0.25	0.33	0.36
Consistency Ratio				0.07
Community Relation & Outreach	CA	BC	MR	Priority
Competitive Advantage	0.23	0.27	0.21	0.23
Board Compositions	0.33	0.37	0.41	0.38
Mutual Relations	0.41	0.38	0.39	0.38
Consistency Ratio				0.004

The table 3 also describes the sub dimensions same as PCJMA in main dimensions, and the consistency ratio is also calculated as per the suggestions of (Saaty, 1980) and the consistency ratio should not be more than 1 if it is over that then is termed as inconsistent and hence the value has to be less than 1. As for what was discovered above, if all of the above values are 0 it will be referred to as consistent. Except from that all the table lies under table 3 indicate that consistency ratio is far below 1. The following equation 1 demonstrates that all the proposed values are accurate and appropriate to compile PCJM. Author has used Expert Choice for the structure of PCJM and for finding the consistency and for cross validation, these two are executed in excel. Besides that, to make use of normalize weights for the next process of finding was to find the global weights as depicted in below table 4 global and local weights of dimensions and sub- dimensions of all.

Table 04---Synthesis Normalized Weights

Goal	Dimensions	Local Weights	Sub Dimensions	Local Weights	Global Weights
	Monitoring Organizational Performance	0.173	• MBO	0.351	0.061
			• Balanced Score Card	0.309	0.053
			• Total Quality Management	0.339	0.059
	Financial Oversight	0.153	• Return on Assets	0.220	0.034
			• Financial leverage	0.314	0.048
			• Liquidity	0.466	0.071
	Evaluating the CEO	0.200	• Merger & acquisitions	0.529	0.106
			• Earning Management	0.224	0.045
			• Intellectual Capital	0.247	0.050
	Providing guidance and support to CEO	0.164	• Incentive alignment	0.490	0.081
			• Leadership	0.237	0.039
			• Social Factors	0.273	0.045
	Fundraising	0.182	• Funding Proposal	0.310	0.057
			• Capital Reserve Funds	0.339	0.062
			• Investment Policy	0.351	0.064
• Competitive advantage			0.239	0.035	
Community relation & outreach	0.147	• Board Compositions	0.373	0.055	
		• Mutual Relations	0.387	0.057	
Total		1.0			1.0

If comparing with the above table 4 we can explicate the value of normalize weights with concern to the local and global weights. From the lesson, we can observe that the most relevant factor linked with board rooms is the extending evaluation of the CEO with the highest value of 0. 20 among main dimension, On the other hand fundraising is the second most associated factor having local weight of 0. 18 can be further classified into sub dimensions of funding proposal is 0. Thirty-one stands capital control reserve funds, zero stands capital capitalizing reserve funds. The mean values assigned to Restrictions 20, Exchange controls 14, Convertibility 11, Trade policy 9, Tariff policy 8, Competition policy 4, Economic integration 3, and investment policy 0. 35. Moreover, among main dimensions out react elaborates the least value of 0 and community relation and out react details the utmost value of 0. 14 among main factors. The existence of the sub din has less information density but the highest values are made of 0. Regarding the number of merger and acquisition strategies, it is necessary to indicate that 5 of them can be grouped with the main dimension of assessing the CEO in relation to other dimensions, which are earning management and intellectual capital with 0. 22, 0. 24 respectively. On the other hand, sub-

dimension competitive advantage reveals the lowest index of local weight with a weight of 0.239 as compare to board compositions and Mutual relations 324 stand to. 37, 0.38 in relation to community relations and outreach activities.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

This research will elaborate regarding the dimension and sub dimensions involving the board room arrangement. This research also reveals that assessing the CEO and fundraising are indicating in line with positive sentiment towards the boardrooms. Importance factors by which the efficiency of boardrooms was evaluated include boards' policies and further clarification of individual roles and responsibilities are higher qualities board prospects represent high merger, simpler and acquisitions that defines a clear way to invest in an appropriate manner rather than earning management and high- intellectual capital that could be available by putting CEOs as high-profile board members that can evaluate individual performances to drive accurate members. Furthermore, fundraising is also, a persistent factor that is very much appealing towards boardrooms with sub dimensions of funding proposal it will also give enhanced perception of the financial situations and operation these fundraising activities occur in various sector to strategize for probable losses that may occur. However, certain aspect of advisory level might have a positive correlation with the company financial and operational performance and thus future research could be done on psychological and behavioural analysis of the study of the nature of structure while looking for the diversity of the board also should consider some other financial factors for assessing performance.

With reference to any organization some factors could also be evaluated with respect to any future direction of any organization even own a level business family. Of course, most and least critical scenarios could be identified and these factors will align with boardrooms to develop efficient processes.

6. References

1. Abdullah, L., Jaafar, S., & Taib, I. (2013). Ranking of human capital indicators using analytic hierarchy process. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral sciences*, 22-28
2. Aguilera, R. V., & Jackson, G. (2010). Comparative and international corporate governance. *Academy of Management annals*, 4(1), 485-556.
3. Arslan, A. M., Agatz, N., Kroon, L., & Zuidwijk, R. (2019). Crowdsourced delivery—A dynamic pickup and delivery problem with ad hoc drivers. *Transportation Science*, 53(1), 222-235.
4. Barzilai, J., Goolany, D., & Goolany, B. (1987). Consistent weights for judgements matrices of the relative importance of alternatives. *Operation Research*, 6, 131-134.
5. Becker, G. S. (1962). Investment in human beings. *Journal of political economy*, 70(5), 9-49.
6. Borlea, S. N., Achim, M. V., & Mare, C. (2017). Board characteristics and firm performances in emerging economies. Lessons from Romania. *Economic research-Ekonomiska istraživanja*, 30(1), 55-75.
7. Cadbury, A. (1992). Report of the committee on the financial aspects of corporate governance (Vol. 1). Gee.
8. Cavaco, S., Crifo, P., Rebérioux, A., & Roudaut, G. (2017). Independent directors: Less

- informed but better selected than affiliated board members? *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 43, 106-121.
9. Chen, J., Leung, W. S., & Goergen, M. (2017). The impact of board gender composition on dividend pay-outs. *Journal of Corporate finance*, 43, 86-105.
 10. Conger, J. A., Finegold, D., & Lawler, E. E. (1998). Appraising boardroom performance. *Harvard business review*, 76, 136-164.
 11. Demb, A., & Neubauer, F. F. (1992). The corporate board: Confronting the paradoxes. *Long range planning*, 25(3), 9-20.
 12. Fama, E. F., & Jensen, M. C. (1983). Separation of ownership and control. *The journal of law and Economics*, 26(2), 301-325.
 13. Farag, H., & Mallin, C. (2017). Board diversity and financial fragility: Evidence from European banks. *International Review of Financial Analysis*, 49, 98-112.
 14. Forbes, D. P., & Milliken, F. J. (1999). Cognition and corporate governance: Understanding boards of directors as strategic decision-making groups. *Academy of management review*, 24(3), 489-505.
 15. Green, J. C., & Griesinger, D. W. (1996). Board performance and organizational effectiveness in nonprofit social services organizations. *Non-profit management and leadership*, 6(4), 381-402.
 16. Gulzar, M. A., & Wang, Z. (2010). Corporate governance and non-listed family owned businesses: an evidence from Pakistan. *International Journal of Innovation, Management and Technology*, 1(2), 124.
 17. Goodhew, G. (2009). Meeting the needs of gifted and talented students London Continuum international publishing program.
 18. Herman, E. S. (1981). *Corporate control, corporate power* (Vol. 98, p. 1). New York: Cambridge University Press.
 19. Herman, R. D., & Renz, D. O. (1997). Multiple constituencies and the social construction of non-profit organization effectiveness. *Non-profit and voluntary sector quarterly*, 26(2), 185-206.
 20. Hillman, A. J., & Dalziel, T. (2003). Boards of directors and firm performance: Integrating agency and resource dependence perspectives. *Academy of Management review*, 28(3), 383-396.
 21. Hu, H. W., Tam, O. K., & Tan, M. G. S. (2010). Internal governance mechanisms and firm performance in China. *Asia Pacific Journal of Management*, 27(4), 727-749.
 22. Idrees, M. A., Khan, A., Abbas, I., & Khan, M. F. (2022). Impact of Microfinance on Small and Medium Enterprise Growth: A Case Study of Pakistan. *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government* Vol, 28(01).
 23. Ikkäheimonen, T. (2014). The board of directors as a part of family business governance—multilevel participation and board development. Ph. D. dissertation, Lappeenranta University of Technology, Lappeenranta.
 24. Kang, H., Cheng, M., & Gray, S. J. (2007). Corporate governance and board composition: Diversity and independence of Australian boards. *Corporate Governance: An International Review*, 15(2), 194-207.
 25. Korent, D., Đunđek, I., & Klačmer Čalopa, M. (2014). Corporate governance practices and firm performance measured by Croatian Corporate Governance Index (CCGI®). *Economic research-Ekonomska istraživanja*, 27(1), 221-231.
 26. Koutra, C., Ali, K., Suleiman, A. D., & Shammout, A. B. (2018). Environmental influences on the exercise of leadership in a family textiles business in Pakistan. *Journal of Hotel and Business Management*, 7(176), 2169-0286.
 27. Ladki, S. M., & Ahmad, F. A. (2018). The Effectiveness of Boards of Directors in Non-profit Organizations. *J Bus Fin Aff*, 7(332), 2167-0234.
 28. Lambert, R. A., Larcker, D. F., & Weigelt, K. (1993). The structure of organizational incentives. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 438-461.
 29. Le Breton-Miller, I., & Miller, D. (2009). Agency vs. stewardship in public family firms: A social embeddedness reconciliation. *Entrepreneurship theory and practice*, 33(6), 1169-

-
- 1191.
30. Lorsch, J., & Young, J. (1990). Pawns or potentates: The reality of America's corporate boards. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 4(4), 85-87.
 - 31.
 32. Lootsma, F. A. (1980). Saaty's priority theory and the nomination of a senior professor in operations research. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 380-388.
 33. Mace, M. (1986). *Directors: Myth and reality* Harvard Business School Press. Boston, MA.
 34. Marinova, J., Plantenga, J., & Remery, C. (2016). Gender diversity and firm performance: Evidence from Dutch and Danish boardrooms. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 27(15), 1777-1790.
 35. McNulty, T., & Pettigrew, A. (1999). Strategists on the board. *Organization studies*, 20(1), 47-74.
 36. Miller, J. L. (2002). The board as a monitor of organizational activity: The applicability of agency theory to non-profit boards. *Non-profit management and leadership*, 12(4), 429-450.
 37. Rediker, K. J., & Seth, A. (1995). Boards of directors and substitution effects of alternative governance mechanisms. *Strategic management journal*, 16(2), 85-99.
 38. Saaty, T. L. (1980). *The analytic hierarchy process*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
 39. Siciliano, J. I. (1996). The relationship of board member diversity to organizational performance. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 15(12), 1313-1320.
 40. Terjesen, S., Couto, E. B., & Francisco, P. M. (2016). Does the presence of independent and female directors impact firm performance? A multi-country study of board diversity. *Journal of Management & Governance*, 20(3), 447-483.
 41. Tarus, D. K., & Aime, F. (2014). Board demographic diversity, firm performance and strategic change: A test of moderation. *Management Research Review*. 37(12). 1110-1136
 42. Van Essen, M., van Oosterhout, J. H., & Carney, M. (2012). Corporate boards and the performance of Asian firms: A meta-analysis. *Asia Pacific Journal of Management*, 29(4), 873-905.
 43. Wade, J., O'Reilly III, C. A., & Chandratat, I. (1990). Golden parachutes: CEOs and the exercise of social influence. *Administrative science quarterly*, 587-603.
 44. Zajac, E. J., & Westphal, J. D. (1994). The costs and benefits of managerial incentives and monitoring in large US corporations: When is more not better? *Strategic management journal*, 15(S1), 121-142.
 45. Zattoni, A., Gnan, L., & Huse, M. (2015). Does family involvement influence firm performance? Exploring the mediating effects of board processes and tasks. *Journal of Management*, 41(4), 1214-1243.